

Multifunctional Chiral Negative Poisson's ratio (Auxetic) Honeycomb Cores with Embedded Piezo-ceramic Patches.

W. Miller¹, C.W. Smith¹, F.L. Scarpa², H. Abramovich³, K.E. Evans¹.

1. School of Engineering Computer Science and Mathematics, University of Exeter, EX4 4QF, Exeter, UK.
2. Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol, BS8 1TR, Bristol, UK.
3. Faculty of Aerospace Engineering, Technion, I.I.T., 32000 Haifa, Israel.

W.Miller@exeter.ac.uk

SUMMARY

This paper describes a new class of chiral honeycombs with embedded piezo-ceramic patches for sensing or actuation. It also demonstrates how the geometry of such honeycombs can be optimised for load bearing, via parametric finite element modelling.

Keywords: Negative Poisson's ratio, Chiral, Honeycomb, Multifunctional, Piezo-ceramic

Introduction

Honeycomb structures are widely used in engineering applications such as sandwich panels due to their high stiffness to weight ratio. A relative new class of honeycombs with chiral cell geometries display the counter intuitive negative Poisson's ratio (they are auxetic), that is they expand laterally when stretched longitudinally [1-7]. These honeycombs can be made with embedded pzt transducers for sensing or actuation functionality. Chiral structures display rotational, but not reflective symmetry, i.e. they cannot be superimposed upon their mirror image. The chiral honeycombs presented in this work consist of cylinders connected with tangential ligaments with either 4 or 6 connectivity, called hexachiral and tetrachiral. A structure displaying both rotational and reflective symmetry is also considered and is called 'tetra anti-chiral', Figure 1. Hexachiral structures were originally proposed by R Lakes *et al* [3, 4], although the chiral topology and its auxetic behaviour had previously been identified by Wojciechowski [5]. The use of a combination of cylinders and ribs provides the possibility to partially decouple the out of plane shear and compression loading because the cylinders provide enhanced compressive strength, while the ligaments resist shear, enabling the tailoring of honeycomb sandwich cores to specific applications.

Auxetic honeycomb structures are proposed because they display high in-plane shear stiffness and synclastic curvature, that is, they form domes rather than saddle structures, making them ideal for consideration as next generation sandwich cores [6]. Auxetic honeycombs also have potential in radomes with their optimised mechanical and dielectric properties [7], and in adaptive and deployable structures [8].

Chiral structures deform with an inherent handedness and undergo a rotative deformation under axial loading, i.e. the chiral structure rotates when loaded in tension or compression, it is therefore necessary to describe their behaviour using a generalized continuum representation known as Cosserat elasticity [9]. Chiral honeycombs are suited for use with embedded PZT type actuators due to the connectivity between ribs and cylinders. When an actuator puts a rib into flexure it causes the attached cylinders to rotate, this in turn causes other ribs to flex and hence adjacent cylinders to rotate. The deformation of ribs and rotation of cylinders is therefore constrained to be similar, unlike in centro-symmetric honeycombs. This work demonstrates a multifunctional honeycomb concept could be used to produce application-tailored structures with embedded structural health monitoring functionality.

Methods

Samples were produced using selective laser sintering of Nylon powder (Duraform) and vacuum casting, dimensions and dimensions were accurate to +/- 0.1 mm throughout (Figure 2). The vacuum casting resin was mixed and the cast under vacuum, this prevents air being mixed into the resins and removes any gasses produced during cure. The resin used was 8040 2-part resin (MCP Equipment), which was chosen for its relatively low viscosity and is well suited to casting structures with high aspect ratio features, such as the ligaments in the chiral structures. Piezo electric MFC patches (Smart Materials Corp., Sarasota, FL 34236) were placed in the mould prior to casting and held in place with spacers of the bulk resin material.

The tetrachiral unit cell structure containing the embedded PZT patch was modelled using ANSYS Multiphysics code [ANSYS 11.0., ANSYS Inc] using 3 DOF SOLID45 8-node brick elements. The piezoelectric patch was modelled using 3D SOLID226 elements with twenty nodes and up to five degrees of freedom per node and was assumed to have perfect bonding to the host structure, using the glue interaction. The structural finite element modelling was conducted using Abaqus version 6.7-1 (Simulia inc.) using C3D10M 10 node quadratic elements, it was necessary to mesh the entire model using quadratic elements due to the complex thin walled geometry and complex deformation mechanisms. It was found that using the Eigen buckling prediction in Abaqus did not accurately predict the buckling modes for the chiral structures therefore it was necessary to complete full 3d explicit formulation models to accurately predict the flatwise plastic behavior of the chiral structures numerically.

Out of plane mechanical characterisation was carried out using according to ASTM Standard C365-00 “Standard Test Method for Flatwise Compressive Properties of Sandwich Cores” using a 300kN testing systems (Lloyd Instruments LR300k), or at a 4 MN compression testing facility at Doosan Babcock Energy Ltd (Renfrew UK). Testing was carried out on 8x8 arrays of cells in to minimise edge effects. The samples were tested until they buckled and buckling is defined here as displaying a visibly large transverse deformation and a rapid decrease of the resistance to deformation. Stress was calculated using the overall projected area of the honeycomb, not the projected cross

sectional area and engineering strain was used throughout; therefore compressive moduli of the structures stated here are the apparent of modulus of the structures rather than the Young's moduli of the component material.

In plane mechanical properties were tested using a Instron 8872 universal materials testing machine as shown in figure 2. Samples consisting of 8x3 unit cells were tested in the small strain linear elastic region (typically 1% applied strain) and video extensometry (MESSPHYSIK ME 46 video extensometer) was used to measure the lateral deformation to determine the in plane Poisson's ratio. Where necessary the rapid prototyped samples had flat bases built into them during sintering to allow easy mechanical testing, as seen on the hexachiral sample in figure 2.

The cylinders have radius r , the ligaments have length L and the nodes and ligaments have common wall thickness t and depth d (Figure 1). Three dimensionless parameters were used to compare the geometry of the chiral honeycombs: $\alpha=L/r$, $\beta=t/r$ and $\gamma=d/r$.

The dynamic response of the tetrachiral structure with the embedded pzt sensor was examined using a force sensor and a shaker via two bolts connected to one of the corner cylinders. The electromagnetic shaker (Ling Dynamic Systems V406) was used to generate a random force to dynamically excite the sample. The stroke of electromagnetic shaker is driven by a signal generator (MATLAB-dSPACE Interface) and a power amplifier (model LDS PA100E) A scanning laser vibrometer (Polytec PSV-300) was used to sense dynamic response of the tetrachiral structure. The velocity range corresponding to a vibrometer output voltage of 1V was chosen at 1mm/s. Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) acquisition was performed for the signals with a selected bandwidth recorded from 10 to 50 kHz

Results

Figure 3 shows that the hexa and tetrachiral structures do not display the predicted -1 Poisson's ratio [4], but have values of -0.75 and -0.4. The tetra antichiral structure does however have the predicted Poisson's ratio of -1. Figures 4 and 5 show the deformed structures for 10x 10 tetrachiral arrays that have been compressed to failure in the flatwise direction, there is excellent agreement in the deformation modes between the two methods. Figure 7 compares the experimental and modelling results for the flatwise compression and also shows excellent agreement between the two methods.

Figures 7 and 8 shows the output from the pzt patch, used as a sensor, and the scanning laser vibrometer used to measure the dynamic response of the rib at the point at which the pzt patch is located. The transfer function are shown to give excellent agreement for the coupled flexural and torsional modes, 500 – 600 Hz, however for the low frequency out of plane flexural modes the pzt only captures the overall trend of the response and does not capture the magnitude.

Discussion

The chiral structures are shown not to possess the predicted -1 Poisson's ratio, this is due to the sample shearing under loading. As the sample is loaded in compression the ligaments flex and cylinders rotate, in chiral structures the connectivity of the cylinders dictates that they all rotate in the same direction, causing a global deformation to occur. This shearing mechanism competes with the negative Poisson's ratio causing an overall reduction in the magnitude of the auxetic behaviour. In the antichiral samples the Poisson's ratio is almost exactly the predicted -1 value, this is because connectivity of the cylinders is different. In the antichiral structures each cylinder rotates in the opposite direction to its nearest neighbours thereby cancelling out the cumulative rotation effect seen in the chiral samples. This is confirmed experimentally as the global shearing observed in the chiral samples is not seen in the antichiral samples.

The out of plane properties of the panels were both numerically modelled and measured experimentally, it was found that it was necessary to use fully explicit 3d plastic models to accurately predict the buckling behaviour of the chiral structures. The high mesh density required because of the structures thin walls meant that the models took a long time to run (up to 4 weeks on a powerful pc with 4 GB of RAM). These computationally expensive models did however correctly predict the buckling mode and gave reasonable agreement to the buckling load and out of plane modulus for the structures.

It is clear that the PZT transducer is not in the optimum orientation for use with the tetrachiral structure, this is seen in the comparison of the pzt's dynamic response with that of the scanning laser vibrometer. The pzt is capable of accurately detecting the higher frequency response of the structure, but does not accurately capture the magnitude of the lower frequency response, only the general trends. This is likely to be due to orientation of the pzt bars in the patch being aligned better to catch the deformation of the structure for some flexural modes, but not others. The reason this current orientation was chosen was due to the requirement to minimise the length of the wiring embedded in the structure to give a sample with better mechanical performance than if the position of the pzt had been optimised. In order to optimise the embedding of the pzt to capture the low frequency response of the structure it would be necessary to use a PZT transducer with the solder tabs mounded alongside, rather than at the end, the functional area to minimise this problem. This work highlights the requirement that in order to effectively use embedded pzt's to sense deformations of structures it is necessary to fully understand the deformation modes to be sensed, including the dynamic response of the structure and the desired frequency/ vibration mode to be detected in order to optimise the position and orientation of the embedded patch.

Conclusions

This work describes the characterisation and optimisation, using mechanical testing and finite element modelling, of a new class of chiral honeycomb structures. The structures are shown to display a negative Poisson's ratio making them suitable for use as cores in doubly curved sandwich panels and their connectivity makes them excellent candidates for use with embedded piezo-ceramic sensors/ actuators. A tetrachiral sample with an embedded piezo ceramic patch was manufactured, characterised and demonstrated the capability to sense the deformation of the structure under a large frequency range of dynamic loading.

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Figures

Figure 1. The cellular geometries of the chiral, antichiral, and conventional centre-symmetric and hexagonal structures: a) hexachiral, b) tetrachiral, c) tetra anti-chiral d) tetrachiral structure showing nomenclature

Figure 2. In plane compression of 8x3 hexachiral cells, showing video extensometer markers fitted in the cylinders and vacuum cast tetrachiral sample with embedded pzt sensor/ actuator.

Figure 3. Lateral strain plotted against longitudinal strain for the three chiral configurations.

Fig.4. Non-linear flatwise compression of tetra-chiral array of 10x10 cells, showing Von Mises stress.

Fig.5. Flatwise compression of tetra-chiral array of 10x10 cells, showing deformation mode.

Figure 6. Comparing stress strain results for FE models and experimental results for flatwise compression of tetra chiral and antichiral structures.

Figure 7. Magnitude of transfer functions obtained from the SLV and the pzt patch output voltage plotted against frequency of sample mechanical activation.

Figure 8. Finite element model of tetrachiral structure with embedded pzt sensor, showing output voltage from pzt patch.